

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 1 |
January 2022 | Monthly Journal
by TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly Journal by **The World
Association of Scientists & Professionals**
TWASP, United States

Strain Measurement and Numerical Analysis of Composite Plate under Laser Irradiation

Ahmed Muhammad Rehan¹, Wang Gao^{1, 2*}, Li Wenzhe^{1, 2}

¹ College of Information and Communication Engineering, North University of China

² Key laboratory of Dynamic Testing Technology, Taiyuan Shanxi China

Accepted

February 09, 2022

Published

February 21, 2022

Copyright: © The Author(s); **Conflicts of Interest:** There are no conflicts to declare.
Wang Gao

*Corresponding Author:

Funding:

Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness, Spain (Award: EDU2015-70491-R)

How to cite this article (APA): Ahmed Muhammad Rehan, Wang Gao, Li Wenzhe (2022). Strain Measurement and Numerical Analysis of Composite Plate under Laser Irradiation. *North American Academic Research*, 5(2), 78-91. doi:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6191641>

ABSTRACT

With the extensive use of lasers in industries and the military, composite materials are becoming increasingly relevant in the field of laser protection. The huge quantity of heat energy produced by laser irradiation is the primary cause of material plate failure. The temperature field and strain field of the material plate must be examined under laser irradiation. In this article, the damage process of T300/AG80, a carbon fiber epoxy composite material, was observed and investigated at normal, high, and laser irradiation temperatures. The modulation of the strain field on the surface of composite materials during laser irradiation was investigated using numerical modeling and test comparison. The strain field distribution is consistent with the numerically computed temperature and strain field distributions. The numerical model's accuracy has been proved, and the calculation results are valuable for engineering reference.

Keywords

Strain Measurements; Laser Irradiation; Numerical Simulation; Carbon Fiber

1. Introduction

1.1 Overview

Carbon fiber/epoxy tar composites are generally utilized in aeronautics, aviation, military, apparatus producing and different fields because of their high explicit strength, high explicit modulus, basic embellishment process and designable material properties. The gum has great mechanical strength and hotness opposition. In the high-temperature warm field, the tar grid is not difficult to disintegrate at low temperature, remove and even disintegrate at high temperature, and the carbon fiber is not difficult to oxidize, weak crack and disintegrate at high temperature, which causes the gum composites to have extraordinary prompt high-temperature removal opposition, which is of incredible importance in the field of laser assurance. In the field

of aviation, carbon fiber/epoxy pitch composites are steadily supplanting customary materials like ferrous metals and non-ferrous metals and become the primary materials of lightweight and hotness safe designs.

In fiber-supported pitch lattice composites, fiber is the vitally mechanical transporter, and the framework and composite connection point chiefly assume the part of uniform burden and burden move. The mechanical harm level of composites under the activity of laser relates to the harm structure and level of grid and fiber and the difference in interface holding state, that is, the difference in composite mesostructured. Through the exploratory examination on the coupling law and peculiarity among composites and high-energy laser, the harm type of pitch network composites still up in the air, yet there is little examination on the progressions of meso morphology and mechanical properties of sap lattice composites after laser illumination.

2. Literature

2.1 Numerical Simulation

Trial research has different constraints, like gear restrictions, instrument precision, activity mistake, etc. Mathematical reenactment in view of limited component strategy cannot just save a great deal of labor and material assets, yet additionally acquire more steady mathematical arrangements. This is additionally a problem area in the examination of warm field of laser lighted composites. Numerous researchers at home and abroad have utilized this technique to acquire great information examination results. In the early exploration work, most of the logical arrangements or semi insightful arrangements were gotten considering the hotness conduction condition after improving on the suspicions. K. Bmgge [1] gives the computation model and consequences of temperature field created by Gaussian and funnel shaped beat laser radiates illuminating a plate with a specific thickness. J. H. Bechtel [2] talked about the hotness conduction of a few lasers following up on the objective tungsten plate. R. E. Waren et al. [3] for the one-layered case, disregarding the warm radiation, considering that the material retention coefficient relates to temperature and the reaction of the plate under laser illumination on account of gasification or liquefying Z. Scherpe [4] considering the variety of warm properties of materials with temperature, the warm conduction examination model of materials lighted by laser is laid out. M. M. Niclang et al. [5] concentrated on the warming, liquefying and gasification of a semi boundless body lighted by a uniform persistent laser. Peng Yufeng et al. [6] thought about the surface warm convection of a limited thickness medium, determined the three-layered temperature dispersion of the medium material under the activity of a solid laser by utilizing the Green's capacity strategy, and gave the connection between the temperature rise and the fundamental size of the material. Mathematical strategies can reenact more complicated circumstances, so they have drawn in increasingly more consideration. J. K. Chen [7] concentrated on the primary unique reaction of layered composites brought about by quick laser warming. Considering the difference in material qualities with temperature and material removal, the temperature appropriation and hotness misfortune were determined by utilizing the superior Crank-Nicholson limited distinction strategy. Wang CFhen [8] through the investigation of the thermochemical removal instrument of

carbon lattice composites, from mass preservation Based on the standard of energy protection and thermochemical harmony of framework compound response, the comparing thermochemical and thermodynamic removal models are laid out. In view of the limit development brought about by material line removal, the hotness conduction condition is laid out. The variable actual properties of materials are viewed as while settling the temperature field and warm pressure field. The powerful thermodynamic conduct of materials under high temperature removal is portrayed by mathematical reenactment. Yi Fajun et al. [9] utilized limited component programming to mathematically reproduce the appropriation and development of warm pressure in the removal interaction of carbon/phenolic composites, determined the transient temperature field and warm pressure field of the material under the steady hotness stream limit condition, and utilized Cai Hill standard to examine the harm of the material pyrolysis zone.

3. Material and Method

3.1 Test Material

The material is carbon fiber laminated composite T300 / Ag80. Whether the basic mechanical properties test of the material in the early stage, the laser irradiation test process in the later stage, and the analysis prototype of the model established by numerical calculation are based on the composite, which will not be repeated in the following paper. According to the measured room temperature physical property data, the density of the material is 1.55g/cm³, the specific heat capacity is 1.008 J / (g OC), and the brand of carbon fiber in the material is T300; The main resin is epoxy resin: 4,4-diaminodiphenylmethane tetraglycidylamine (AG-80), and the structural formula is:

It can be seen from the chemical structure formula that the material has highly cross-linked four functional groups, so it has good heat resistance. The test piece used in the test is a 10 layer composite structure, and the laying direction of the longitudinal test piece is [45/-45/0/90/O]., Size 140 × 10 × 1.5mm.

4. Experimental Results and Analysis

4.1 Strain Field Analysis

The laser harm of composite constructions is for the most part brought about by warm mechanical coupling or removal, so it is important to test and concentrate on the pressure field of composite plates lighted by laser. The exploratory examination establishes the framework for the harm peculiarity of laser illuminated design, notices the peculiarity, and elucidates a few removal and disappointment components. In any case, as

of now, there are generally more examination work on exploratory perception, however there are not many pertinent investigations on the pressure dispersion trial of composite plate under laser illumination, and precise pressure field test and investigation is the premise of mathematical computation, Therefore, it is important to test, review and dissect this part. For the estimation of dynamic strain of composite plate illuminated by laser, the cronos.pl2.dio dynamic strain check arrangement of IMC organization is utilized to quantify the strain of composite plate lighted by laser, to acquire the variety law of strain field.

To meet the necessities of test exactness more readily, the strain check utilized is a little strain measure to test the strain change in a little region on the composite plate. The model of strain check is bxl20.2aa. The boundariesare opposition is 119.8 ± 0.1 Q, responsiveness coefficient is $2.08 \pm 1\%$, framework length $\times$ The matrix width is 2x LMM and the exactness grade is a. The unique strain check framework has high test exactness, and the experimental outcomes can be precise to 1 miniature strain. The most extreme testing pace of each channel is 100kHz, the voltage input range is ± 5 illv to ± 10 V, and the current info range is ± 100 u a to ± 50 L. The inspecting rate and voltage and current information scope of the test framework meet the test prerequisites. In the test, to control the information size of the outcomes, the examining pace of each channel is set as 50Hz. The trial boundaries are displayed in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1: Experimental parameters

Strain test plan				
Power Spot diameter	Laser power			
	150	50	50	50
Uncoated	1cm	2cm	4cm	6cm
Coated	1cm	2cm	4cm	6cm

Here are four groups of eight composite plates in the strain test. The effects of different irradiation diameters and different laser intensities on the strain field of the composite plates are compared. The pasting methods of strain gauges for composite plates with different diameters, including patch schematic diagram and physical photos, are shown in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1: Distribution schematics of 30mm strain gauge

Figure 4-2: Distribution schematics of 20mm strain gauge

Figure 4-3: Distribution schematics of 10mm strain gauge

Figure 4-4: Distribution schematics of 5mm strain gauge

Under the irradiation of a 50W/cm² laser, the strain changes of upper and lower surfaces at different places in vertical, horizontal, and oblique directions with laser irradiation were evaluated using an uncoated composite plate with radius R=1cm as an example. The distribution of strain sheets on the top and lower surfaces is shown in Figures 4-5 and 4-6.

Figure 4-5: Front surface number chart

Figure 4-6: Back surface number chart

4.2 Analysis of Strain Test

First, let's look at the strain changes of the longitudinal and transverse strain gauges on the front of the composite plate under the irradiation of 50W/cm² laser.

Figure 4-7: Front surface curve of longitudinal strain gauge

Figure 4-8: Front surface curve of longitudinal strain gauge

It tends to be seen from Figure 4-7 and Figure 4-8 that the strain measure near the light spot in the longitudinal and cross over bearings should change enormously, the strain checks a long way from the light spot should change marginally, and the strain is negative, demonstrating that the material plate where the strain check is found is feeling the squeeze. Whenever the laser illuminates the focal point of the composite plate, the light place region is warmed and extended, so it is continually crushed outward, bringing about bad strain in the pressure of the non-laser light region. It tends to be seen from the schematic graph of strain check gluing that the circulation method of strain change is disseminated outward in concentric rings, so the strain worth of strain measure will be more modest thusly. In Figure 4-7 the strain worth of strain check No. 34 started to diminish gradually, and the strain worth of strain check diminished pointedly after around 3.5s. There are two explanations behind the present circumstance. One is that the place of strain measure is exceptionally near the illumination area of laser spot, so the temperature changes significantly, and the paste stuck with strain check might come up short, which straightforwardly prompts test disappointment. The other is that when lighted by laser, there will be clear surface folds on the material plate surface, and the surface folds will move from the focal point of the laser spot to the edge like water waves. Assuming this overlay wave arrives at the position where the strain measure is found or near the strain check, it will create an enormous strain esteem. Obviously, it should be noticed that the peculiarity of extreme worth brought about by either circumstance isn't what the test needs, and these outcomes ought to be eliminated. A comparative circumstance additionally happened in strain check 54, however the mathematical decay process is generally steady, and the last worth is likewise somewhat little. The experimental outcomes have a specific reference esteem.

Presently how about we investigate the sideways 45 of the fronts of the composite plate. Mathematical variety of strain check strain toward every path.

Figure 4-9: Front surface curve of strain gauge at 45 degrees

It very well may be seen from Figure 4-9 that the strain upsides of strain measures 41, 42 and 43, which are far away from the laser illumination, are ordinary, and the mathematical change and conveyance mode are additionally steady with the vertical and even headings. Be that as it may, the strain check 44 nearest to the laser illumination spot starts to show a huge negative strain worth, and afterward goes to a huge positive strain esteem, this is conflicting with the longitudinal and cross over examination. This is on the grounds that the roundabout dispersion of the laser is lopsided. The laser radiates on No. 44 strain measure, or the material consumes after the laser lights the composite plate. The hotness energy brought by the ignition influences No. 44 strain check, bringing about unusual strain changes and wrong last strain esteems. We should look again at the strain changes of the longitudinal, cross over and slanted strain checks on the converse side of the composite plate, that is, the non-laser lighted surface.

Figure 4-10: Back surface curve of longitudinal strain gauge

Figure 4-11: Back surface curve of latitudinal strain gauge

The strain change of the strain check on the non-laser illuminated surface of the material plate is considerably more mind boggling. In Figures 4-10 and 4-11, there is a rising stage wherein the strain measure strain is beneath J toward the start of laser illumination, and the strain worth of the strain check nearer to the light spot is bigger, and the strain of the strain check farther away from the light spot is moderately more modest. This is on the grounds that when the laser starts to illuminate, an effect interaction will be framed on the composite plate, and the strain check behind the plate will have a tractable cycle, bringing about a positive worth. With the further advancement of laser illumination, the warm extension of the focal region of the plate makes each strain check packed and negative. Thusly, the last strain of the strain measure with the biggest strain under the underlying J at the close to end of the spot is the littlest, while the strain check at the most distant finish of the spot is minimal impacted by the laser effect and focal warm extension, so the difference in the bend is gentle. After laser sway, the strain on the facade of the composite plate is likewise negative, so this sway trademark isn't shown. Looking at Figure 4-10 and 4-11 it can likewise be seen that the strain change pattern of No. 14 and negative. 24 strain measures close to the spot is something similar and the worth is exceptionally huge, which shows that the effect of laser illumination on the strain site is mostly packed in the close to region of the laser spot, however considerably less in the far region. This resembles the impact of laser light on temperature, and there is an incredible relationship between's them.

Figure 4-12: Back surface curve of strain gauge at 45 degrees

4.3 Comparing the Results

The numerical simulation of the test process is carried out. The finite element modeling process such as modeling method and parameter setting is consistent with the temperature field analysis process of composite plate. For the strain at the position where the strain gauge is pasted, the central point strain of the element at that position is taken as the standard. First, let's look at the numerical analysis results of the strain of front longitudinal strain gauges 31, 32, 33 and 34, and compare them with the test results to analyze the accuracy of the numerical analysis model.

Figure 4-13: Front surface numerical simulation result of Longitudinal points

As should be visible from Figure 4-13, the strain aftereffect of No. 34 strain measure nearest to the laser spot is the biggest, and the strain esteem aftereffect of No. 31 strain check farthest from the laser spot is the littlest. This change pattern is steady with the experimental outcomes. Nonetheless, it is significant that the strain worth of No. 34 strain measure is a lot bigger than that of other strain checks, which is clearly not

at the very quantitative level as that of the other three strain measures, which shows that the impact of laser light on the strain field is principally packed in the space near the laser illumination spot, and assuming the distance is a little farther, the worth will change extraordinarily. This component is steady with the experimental outcomes, which likewise shows that the strain measure nearest to the laser spot has an enormous strain esteem and is not difficult to harm and come up short during the test. Simultaneously, this element is additionally reliable with the mathematical reenactment consequences of temperature field circulation. Obviously, there should be an association between temperature field appropriation and strain field circulation, which won't be examined a lot here. Then, the examination between the mathematical reenactment consequences of strain field and the strain test results is broke down.

Figure 4-14: Comparatives curves of Strain test

It very well may be seen from the examination Figure 4-14 that the outcome bend of mathematical reproduction is smooth, and the descending pattern is steady, while the experimental outcome bend will vary all over, and there are incredible changes when the descending pattern. In the underlying stage, the strain worth of the mathematical reproduction result is more noteworthy than the experimental outcome, then, at that point, the experimental outcome diminishes forcefully, and it is a lot more prominent than the mathematical reenactment bring about the last stage. At the point when the laser illuminates the material plate, there will be not just the strain change brought about by the extension of the focal point of the material plate, yet additionally the strain change brought about by the outward dissemination temperature. For the strain check near the laser spot, it will be impacted by the conspicuous strain field, yet additionally by the temperature field. The strain field makes the strain esteem negative, however the strain esteem impacted by the temperature is positive, along these lines, the strain mathematical outcomes estimated by the strain check will be impacted partially, bringing about the peculiarity that the mathematical recreation brings about the underlying stage in Figure 4-14 are marginally bigger than the experimental outcomes. Since the hotness impacted area of laser light isn't enormous, the temperature impact is generally little for the strain check a long way from the focal point of the

laser spot. As referenced before, regardless of whether there is the impact of temperature field, this impact isn't extraordinary, and won't be rehashed here. For the bend examination graph, the later experimental outcomes are more prominent than the mathematical reenactment results, which is because of the impact of the warm field brought about by laser light, disappointment, or material plate burning. The unwavering quality of the strain test results at this stage is exceptionally low, the harm and disappointment of the test strain measure can likewise be effectively decided from the pattern of the strain check strain test results. How about we look again at the correlation of the two consequences of No. 43 strain measure near the place of No. 44 strain measure, Figure 4-15.

Figure 4-15: Comparative curve of strain gauge

It tends to be seen from Figure 4-15 that the correlation aftereffects of the two are clearly better compared to that of strain measure 44, demonstrating that the place of strain check 43 has been minimal impacted by the temperature field brought about by laser illumination, the strain measure has not been harmed in the test stage, and is additionally minimal impacted by other ecological variables. Notwithstanding the attributes depicted in the strain examination graph of No. 43 strain measure, one more exceptional component of the strain examination graph of No. 44 strain measure is that the two bends gradually produce a little detachment peculiarity with the development of time. During the time spent mathematical displaying, the energy misfortune during the time spent laser illumination isn't thought of, like hotness dissemination on the outer layer of composite plate, ignition energy utilization, and so forth these elements are unavoidable in the real test, so the aftereffects of mathematical reproduction will be somewhat bigger. This likewise shows that the model utilized in the mathematical reproduction can be additionally improved to get more functional outcomes.

5. Conclusion

The strain field of composite plate lighted by laser is tried and mathematically recreated. The variety of strain field of composite plate with laser light is gotten. The test information is steady with the mathematical recreation results. During the time spent mathematical displaying, the energy misfortune during the time spent

laser light isn't thought of, however these elements are unavoidable in the real test. Consequently, when the laser illumination time is long, the outcome worth of mathematical re-enactment will be somewhat bigger than that of the test. The mathematical examination model utilized in this paper additionally has space for additional improvement, to get more viable mathematical outcomes. The temperature field trial of composite plate under laser illumination is being organized. The mix of temperature field test results and mathematical estimation results can more likely examine and concentrate because of laser illumination on the temperature field of composite plate and give right improvement bearing and sensible improvement measures for working on the properties of T300/AG80 composites.

References

1. Voisey, K.T., S. Fouquet, D. Roy, and T.W. Clyne, Fibre swelling during laser drilling of carbon fibre composites. *Optics and Lasers in Engineering*, 2006. 44(11): p. 1185-1197.
2. Mathew, J., G.L. Goswami, N. Ramakrishnan, and N.K. Naik, Parametric studies on pulsed Nd: YAG laser cutting of carbon fiber reinforced plastic composites. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 1999. 89–90(0): p. 198-203.
3. Negarestani, R., L. Li, H.K. Sezer, D. Whitehead, and J. Methven, Nano-second pulsed DPSS Nd: YAG laser cutting of CFRP composites with mixed reactive and inert gases. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 2010. 49(5-8): p. 553-566.
4. Davim, J.P. and P. Reis, Study of delamination in drilling carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) using design experiments. *Composite Structures*, 2003. 59(4): p. 481-487.
5. Kalla, D., J. Sheikh-Ahmad, and J. Twomey, Prediction of cutting forces in helical end milling fiber reinforced polymers. *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, 2010. 50(10): p. 882-891.
6. Shyha, I.S., D.K. Aspinwall, S.L. Soo, and S. Bradley, Drill geometry and operating effects when cutting small diameter holes in CFRP. *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, 2009. 49(12–13): p. 1008-1014.
7. Li, Z.L., P.L. Chu, H.Y. Zheng, G.C. Lim, L. Li, S. Marimuthu, R. Negarestani, M. Sheikh, and P. Mativenga, Laser machining of carbon fibre-reinforced plastic composites, in *Advances in Laser Materials Processing*, J. Lawrence, et al., Editors. 2010, Woodhead Publishing. p. 136-177.
8. Uhlmann, E., G. Spur, H. Hocheng, S. Liebelt, and C.T. Pan, The extent of laserinduced thermal damage of UD and crossply composite laminates. *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, 1999. 39(4): p. 639-650.
9. Pan, C.T. and H. Hocheng, Evaluation of anisotropic thermal conductivity for unidirectional FRP in laser machining. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2001. 32(11): p. 1657-1667.
10. Muramatsu, M., Y. Harada, T. Suzuki, and H. Niino, Infrared stress measurements of thermal damage to laser-processed carbon fiber reinforced plastics. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2015. 68: p. 242-250.

© 2022 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

